

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

CLASSIFICATION OF THE GEOMETRIC COMPLEXITY OF PRODUCTS MANUFACTURED BY SELECTIVE LASER MELTING TECHNOLOGY

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Abstract

The article describes approaches to the classification of products that manufactured by the technology of selective laser melting during the organization of high-tech production of industrial gas turbine engines with an intelligent system of design and technological preparation to improve their functional characteristics.

The classifier of the geometric complexity of products, developed based on an expert assessment, is part of the intelligent system for the integrated design and technological preparation of the production of parts for industrial gas turbine engines.

Keywords: additive manufacturing, selective laser melting, heat-resistant alloy, configuration.

Introduction

The development of additive technologies in the production of industrial gas turbine products is focused on three main areas:

- for obtaining innovative products: products with new properties and behaviors, increased functional properties, expansion of applicability, increase in resource and reliability, durability;
- manufacturing optimization: reduction of the technological chain, production time and energy consumption;
- production of equipment and tools: printing of master models, casting molds, tools.

The criteria for making decisions on the possibility of manufacturing a product using selective laser melting are:

- weight reduction for large parts;
- combination of parts (joint parts), reduction of assembly restrictions;
- achievement of specific characteristics (in comparison with castings);
- the possibility of bionic forms (effective use of the material).

To organize a quality management system for the additive manufacturing of industrial gas turbine products, it is necessary to determine the complexity of structures and design by categorizing and classifying the geometric complexity, functional purpose of aerospace products according to several parameters: material, properties, service life (resource). This database as classifier should be included in the intellectual system of integrated design and technological preparation for the production of parts for industrial gas turbine engines.

To define a constructive complexity is considered the expert method. The main task of the design and technological reproduction of additive manufacturing is to determine the criteria for the complexity of the geometry of the product for making decisions on the choice of technological parameters, determining the labor intensity and cost of manufacturing.

In this work, the object of design and technological preparation of additive manufacturing is the assembly unit "Burner device". Figure 1 shows the technology of selective laser melting (SLM) of metal powder of high-temperature alloy. This design consists of four main parts: housing, swirler, nozzle bushing, nozzle.

Figure 1. The design of the assembly unit "Burner device", optimized for the SLM method

Classifier description

The assignment of parts to a particular group of complexity can be performed according to the following criteria:

- the first group - elongated parts such as bodies of revolution. The ratio of length to diameter of such parts is greater than one;
- the second group - details like gas turbine disks;
- the third group - simple in configuration box-shaped flat parts;
- fourth group - closed box-type body parts;
- fifth group - large and heavy box-shaped parts (bearing structures).

To determine the complexity factor of a product, it is necessary to determine and evaluate its configuration, namely the number of structural elements that ensure the complexity of the design itself.

To determine the criteria for the complexity of aerospace products manufactured by selective laser melting technology, the following parameters in the Classifier are used:

- *images* of the structure (views, sections, sections, remote elements). So a detail of a complex configuration has many different construction elements: stepped surfaces, holes, grooves, rounding radii, chamfers, stiffeners, etc., which, in turn, increases the number of views, cuts and sections, remote elements;

- *dimensions* for the manufacture and control of the product. Precise seating surfaces, precise guide surfaces, etc. cause the application of a large number of sizes;

- *tolerances* of the shape and location of surfaces, the basis for the manufacture and control of the product. Simple designs of assembly units and parts do not have exact tolerances for the shape and location of surfaces, and for complex ones, it is necessary to apply a large number of bases, tolerances for the shape and location of surfaces;

- *surface roughness*. For assembly units with a large number of machined surfaces, it is necessary to apply a large number of surface roughness designations.

Four groups (classes) of complexity of aviation and aerospace products manufactured by additive technologies were determined by the expert method based on the analysis of the above parameters. The description of the complexity groups and the value of the complexity coefficients are presented in Table 1.

The main indicators of the complexity of the geometry of the product is the complexity of the design and execution of design documentation, which depends on the number of dimensions that are controlled and thereby determine the configuration of the product.

Table 1

Categories of complexity of products manufactured by additive technologies

Group (class) of complexity	Description	Indicator of complexity
1	2	3
I	Details of simple shapes that do not require complex CAD / CAE calculations, auxiliary elements in the design of the product. The specification contains a small number of items. For example, bushings, simple levers and brackets, housings, etc. Material: stainless, tool steels	1,0
II	Details of simple shapes, having several working surfaces, protrusions or depressions that do not require special CAD / CAE calculations. The specification contains a small amount positions, the presence of notes indicating the selection, permissible replacement of components. For example: flanges, brackets, housings, etc. Material: aluminum alloys	1,2
III	Details of complex shapes with a combination of straight and curved working surfaces that require CAD / CAE calculations for their design. Assembly units, including cast and welded hull and non-hull parts with a straight and curved surface, assembly units operating under pressure, high temperatures. Assembly units, the design of which is associated with design calculations, but does not require search work. The specification contains a large number of positions, an indication of the zones, the presence of notes indicating the selection, the permissible replacement of components. For example: flame tube, swirler Material: high temperature alloys, materials with special properties	1,5
IV	Details of complex shapes with a large number of measurements and mating surfaces that require special CAD / CAE calculations, taking into account increased requirements in determining tolerances. Assembly units containing complex surfaces and structural elements that require calculations of a large number of mating dimensions, having cast and welded elements of complex configuration. Assembly units, the design of which requires partial search work with test work. The specification contains a large number of positions, an indication of the zones, the presence of notes indicating the selection, the permissible replacement of components. For example: assembly unit "Burner device", topologically optimized bracket Material: high temperature alloys, titanium alloys	2,0

In general, the complexity criterion for a product manufactured by additive technologies can be represented as a one-dimensional matrix 1:

$$Q(x) = \{\alpha_1 q_1(x), \alpha_2 q_2(x), \dots, \alpha_n q_n(x)\} \quad (1)$$

where q_n – local criteria characterizing the configuration of the product: the criterion of elementary surfaces; criterion of straight lines, criterion of interpolation curves; form constraint criterion; criterion for surfaces obtained by rotating a curve around an axis; criterion for surfaces obtained by moving a curve along a guide curve, etc.; α – weighting factor for the local criterion.

The characteristic that defines the characteristic is a method of searching and calculating. The local complexity criterion of product complexity $q_n(x)$ can be represented as dependence 2:

$$q_n(x) = F(D_i, WD_i, C) \quad (2)$$

where D_i – characteristic of local complexity criterion, WD_i – interval, C – category.

Method for determining a local complexity criterion:

Analysis *.step product file: definition of D_i according to the relevant indications L_{ij} according to dependency 3:

$$D_i = \sum L_{ij} \quad (3)$$

So, for example, if as a characteristic of a local criterion q_1 select D_1 – the number of dimensions of elementary surfaces, then we will take into account the following features L_{ij} :

– L_{11} – sign of planes in the geometry of the product;

- L_{12} – sign of spherical surfaces in product geometry;
- L_{13} – sign of solid cylinders in the product geometry.

2) Based on the characteristics D_i and the table of intervals WD_i the complexity category C is determined for each local criterion q in accordance with dependence 4:

$$WD_i[C] = D_i$$

$$D_i C_j = \left[\min D_i C_j \dots \max D_i C_j \right] \quad (4)$$

Table 2 of intervals for each characteristic is determined by an expert based on the experience of the work of the laboratory of additive technologies, and is a two-dimensional matrix $D_i C_j$.

Table 2

Boolean values of local complexity criteria	
Boolean values of local complexity criteria	Value
Elementary	1
Very simple	2
Simple	3
Normal	4
Moderate	5
Complex	6
High complex	7
High	8
Definitely high	9
Indefinitely high	10

Result discussion

The definition of intervals WD_i is carried out in accordance with the following algorithm:

- choice of characteristic assembly units;
- expert analysis of assembly units;
- grouping of unique details;

$$\min D_i C_1 = \min D_i (C_1); \max D_i C_1 = \max D_i (C_1);$$

$$\min D_i C_j = \max D_i C_{j-1} + 1; \max D_i C_j = \max D_i (C_j), j = [2 - 9]; \quad (5)$$

$$\min D_i C_{10} = \max D_i C_9 + 1; \max D_i C_{10} = \min D_i (C_9) \cdot S;$$

where S – uncertainty factor, $S = 1,5$.

- calculation of a single criterion of complexity for a part;
- calculation of complexity characteristics of the geometry of assembly units;

- calculation of the characteristics of the complexity of the part;

- calculation of the table of part intervals: for example, for category 1 of complexity in accordance with dependence 5:

- calculation of the table of intervals of assembly units.

The assembly unit "Burner device" was chosen (Figure 2). This Part was assigned the ninth level of difficulty category.

Figure 2 – Burner device

Assembly unit "Burner device" consists of four parts: housing, swirler, nozzle sleeve, nozzle. At the same time, these details have different levels of complexity:

- housing – local complexity criteria (difficulty level): 7;
- swirler - local complexity criteria (difficulty level): 8;
- nozzle – local complexity criteria (difficulty level): 4;
- nozzle sleeve - local complexity criteria (difficulty level): 3.

The proposed categorization of aerospace products manufactured by additive technologies makes it possible to more accurately determine the labor intensity, typical technological solutions and production costs in accordance with the accepted quality management system.

Conclusion

The article describes an approach to the classification of products manufactured using the technology of selective laser melting in the organization of high-tech production of industrial gas turbine engines with

an intelligent system of design and technological preparation to improve their functional characteristics. 4 classes and 9 levels of product complexity are determined by the expert method.

The "Burner Device", manufactured by the selective laser melting, is assigned to the 9th level of complexity by local complexity criterion and the 4th class: details of complex shapes with a large number of measurements and mating surfaces that require special CAD / CAE calculations, taking into account increased requirements in determining tolerances, containing complex surfaces and structural elements that require calculations of a large number of mating dimensions, having cast and welded elements of complex configuration with test work.

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